

Fig. 2. Part of a “virtual rice field,” an example of the simulation output.

could be done by changing the values of parameters controlling leaf shape and by using image-processing software to analyze the output. More extensive investigations of the interactions between morphogenesis and the environment, however, will re-

quire virtual rice to be interfaced with an ecophysiological model. This will enable expression of partitioning, calculated by the physiological model, in 3D structure. This is in preparation for analysis of effects on, for example, competition for resources and optimi-

zation of plant population density. Thus, virtual rice has the potential to become a valuable framework for integrating research results from different disciplines and for communicating research output to farmers and others in the form of scientific visualization.

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Source-sink characteristics of japonica/indica hybrid rice

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Poor grain filling is the main barrier to using heterosis of japonica/indica hybrid rice (J/I-HR) (Wang et al 1991, Yuan 1990). This study aimed to explain the causes of poor grain filling by investigating the source-sink relations of 36 J/I-HR combinations. Six japonica lines with wide compatibility genes—PC 311, Lunhui 422, Jw-8, Ce-01, 02428, and Ce-03—were used as female parents

and six typical indica lines—Milyang 23, 3037, Zaixiandang-18, IR36, Minghui 63, and Yangdao 4—were used as male parents to make 36 first-generation J/I-HR combinations by the P × Q mode, that is, the females (P) were crossed to the males (Q). An indica hybrid rice combination, Shanyou 63, was used as a control. Seedlings were raised in a greenhouse and transplanted

into the rice field on the Yangzhou University farm, Jiangsu Province, China (32°30’N, 119°25’E) during the 1997 rice-growing season (May–Oct). The experiment was repeated in 1998. Source-sink characteristics were determined by measuring sink size (defined as spikelet number m⁻²), content of nonstructural carbohydrate (NSC) in culms and sheaths, and dry matter accumulation before

and after heading. Flag leaves on the main stems were labeled with ^{14}C at heading to examine ^{14}C -assimilate partitioning in the plants.

The average sink size of J/I-HR was large (55,000 spikelets m^{-2}), which was 30% and 21% larger than the average of the parents and of Shanyou 63, respectively (Table 1). J/I-HR combinations had obvious heterosis in dry matter production. Their average dry matter accumulation during the grain-filling period was 59% and 105% higher than the average of the parents and Shanyou 63, respectively, resulting in a high ratio of source to sink (dry weight/spikelet). The heterosis in dry matter production of J/I-HR was attributed to the large leaf area index at heading and high photosynthetic potential from heading to harvest (Table 1). The higher source-sink ratio indicated that poor grain filling of J/I-HR may not result from "large sink size without enough source" as reported before (Yuan 1997, Zhuang et al 1994).

However, J/I-HR poorly remobilized assimilates from vegetative tissues to grains. The transfer ratio of total NSC to grains, the apparent percentage of remobilized carbon reserves in the culm and sheath, and the harvest index of the J/I-HR combinations were much lower than those of their parents and Shanyou 63. At maturity, only 48% of the ^{14}C fed to flag leaves was partitioned into grains for J/I-HR, vs 82% for Shanyou 63 (Table 2). The poor remobilization of assimilates may be attributed to weak sink strength and delayed senescence (keeping "green" for too long at maturity) in J/I-HR (Wang et al 1998). Re-

Table 1. Source-sink characteristics of japonica/indica hybrid rice (J/I-HR) combinations, their parents, and Shanyou 63.

Source-sink characteristic	Source		
	J/I-HR	Parents	Shanyou 63
Spikelets ($\text{no.} \times 10^6 \text{ ha}^{-1}$)	534.0 \pm 45 ^b	411.0 \pm 46	443.0
Leaf area index at heading	7.8 \pm 0.5	6.0 \pm 1.1	7.3
Photosynthetic potential ($\text{m}^2 \text{ d}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$) ^a	175.0 \pm 13.0	142.0 \pm 15.0	157.0
Dry matter weight (t ha^{-1})			
At heading	12.0 \pm 1.4	8.9 \pm 1.5	12.0
Heading to maturity	9.5 \pm 0.9	6.0 \pm 1.1	4.6
Dry weight spikelet ⁻¹ (mg)			
At heading	22.5 \pm 2.3	21.8 \pm 2.5	28.0
Heading to maturity	17.2 \pm 1.2	14.5 \pm 1.3	10.5

^aExpressed as green leaf area $\text{d}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ from heading to maturity. ^bData are expressed as means \pm standard errors (SE). Samples (n) = 36 combinations for J/I-HR, 12 lines for the parents, and 1 combination for Shanyou 63. Each measurement is from 50 plants from each combination/line.

Table 2. Transport of assimilates of japonica/indica hybrid rice (J/I-HR) combinations, their parents, and Shanyou 63.

Transport of assimilates	Source		
	J/I-HR	Parents	Shanyou 63
Remobilized C reserves (%) ^a	7.5 \pm 5.2 ^d	43.7 \pm 7.3	78.7
Transfer ratio of assimilates (%) ^b	62.4 \pm 6.1	78.1 \pm 7.3	93.3
Harvest index	0.4 \pm 0.03	0.4 \pm 0.06	0.5
NSC residue (mg g^{-1} DW) ^c	196.0 \pm 11.0	172.0 \pm 12.0	89.0
^{14}C partitioning (%)			
Panicle	48.3 \pm 3.2	67.2 \pm 4.9	81.6
Culm + sheath + leaf	51.7 \pm 4.8	32.8 \pm 5.1	18.4

^a[Nonstructural carbohydrate (NSC) in culms and sheaths at heading (a) – NSC in culms and sheaths at maturity]/a \times 100.

^b(Panicle weight at maturity – panicle weight at heading)/(NSC in culms and sheaths at heading + dry weight of plant at maturity – dry weight of plant at heading) \times 100. ^cNSC remaining in culms and sheaths at maturity. ^dData are expressed as means \pm standard errors (SE). Samples (n) = 36 combinations for J/I-HR, 12 lines for the parents, and 1 combination for Shanyou 63. Each measurement is from 50 plants from each combination/line.

sults suggest that poor transport of assimilates to grains accounted for the poor grain filling of J/I-HR. Grain filling could be improved by enhancing the translocation and remobilization of assimilates to the grain through breeding and crop management.

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